

StateProc: Empowering Network Functions With Enhanced Processing Capabilities in Edge Clouds

Mahdi Attawna^{*}, Tung V. Doan[†], Frank H.P. Fitzek^{*‡}, Giang T. Nguyen^{†‡}

^{*}*Deutsche Telekom Chair of Communication Networks, TU Dresden, Germany*

[†]*Haptic Communication Systems, TU Dresden, Germany*

[‡]*Centre for Tactile Internet with Human-in-the-Loop (CeTI)*

E-mails: {mahdi.attawna|tung.doan_van|frank.fitzek|giang.nguyen}@tu-dresden.de

Abstract—Edge clouds embrace Network Function Virtualization (NFV) to bring network functions (NFs) closer to end devices. The mobility nature of edge clouds and the emergence of new use cases, such as robot control or metaverse, demand NFs with high resilience. However, numerous NFs like firewalls require stateful processing that depends on historical processing values, referred to as NF states. Consequently, supporting stateful NFs with high resilience necessitates the maintenance of their states, often resulting in significant modification of the NFs. While providing high resilience for NFs, maintaining their processing performance is a critical challenge for existing solutions. Our proposed framework, StateProc, eliminates this concern by enhancing the processing capabilities of NFs through the utilization of NF states for custom processing. Through custom processing for state transfer, the evaluation results show that StateProc significantly improves the state transfer time, up to 93% faster than a notable state-of-the-art framework, without additional processing overhead.

Index Terms—Network Function Virtualization, Edge Computing, State Management, Low-latency, Flexibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network Function Virtualization (NFV) has played an inevitable role in centralized clouds that rely on numerous network functions (NFs), such as cloud firewalls [1], to improve the performance of cloud services for a continuously growing number of end devices. Due to the centralized design, cloud providers consolidate computation and storage resources to form large-scale data centers in certain locations. Subsequently, end devices frequently experience significant transmission delays because of the geographical distance from centralized clouds. Considering the emergence of latency-sensitive use cases such as remote surgery and metaverse, such delays are intolerable, thus making centralized clouds ill-suited. To tackle this issue, edge clouds have been introduced to offer computation and storage resources at the edge of networks, allowing NFs to support cloud services near end devices with minimal latency.

Along with the benefits of NFV in edge clouds, it is well-known that maintaining NFs faces tremendous challenges. NF failure could lead to network outages and consequently interrupt various cloud services. Fault tolerance must prevent service interruption by rapidly recovering NFs in response to failures. Moreover, the scaling of NFs, which involves adjusting the number of NF instances on demand, frequently occurs as a reaction to fluctuations in cloud traffic. More

importantly, the mobility of end devices in edge clouds often necessitates the migration of NFs from one edge server to another. Meanwhile, numerous NFs require stateful processing that relies on NF states (i.e., historical processing data) to ensure appropriate processing behaviors. Maintaining stateful NFs in edge clouds requires low-latency state transfer between NF instances guaranteeing state consistency, meaning each NF instance has the latest states from other instances.

Prior studies have been proposed to modify NFs to support the transfer of NF states for use cases such as fault tolerance and scaling. Early studies have proposed state management frameworks in centralized clouds, such as Split/Merge [2] and OpenNF [3], to control the state transfer between NFs, i.e., receiving states from one NF and forwarding them to another NF. Since the involvement of state management frameworks introduces significant state transfer time, notable studies such as [4] and [5] have proposed to perform direct state transfer between NFs, thus making them well-suited in edge clouds. However, modifying NFs for state transfer is challenging due to the significant effort required to understand the NF architecture. Moreover, the modification must be meticulous to ensure that the processing performance of NFs is maintained.

To address the above concerns, we leverage NF states to enhance the processing capabilities of NFs. Our idea builds on the fact that stateful NFs inherently provide *fixed functionalities* dependent on *NF states* to handle packets. For instance, a stateful firewall collects packet information from incoming traffic and use them to decide whether to drop or pass packets. We aim to provide *extra functionalities* (i.e., custom processing) for NFs, leveraging either their own states or the states of other NFs to handle packets. Taking a chain consisting of a stateful firewall and a Network Address Translator (NAT) as an example, the firewall can obtain states from the NAT and use them to perform the NAT functionalities (i.e., translating IP addresses), thus reducing latency.

We propose StateProc, a state management framework that allows to utilize NF states to enhance the processing capabilities of NFs for various use cases, such as fault tolerance and scaling. Furthermore, we propose a novel state transfer scheme within StateProc that employs a batching technique to aggregate NF states, thus reducing the number of transfers required for NF states over the network and minimizing state

transfer time. The experimental results show that StateProc reduces state transfer time by 93% compared to FAST [5], a notable state-of-art study.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews various techniques in the literature for state management. We first discuss studies in centralized clouds, which assume abundant computing and bandwidth resources for the state transfer of NFs. These approaches incur significant downtime, making them unsuitable for NFs in edge clouds, where low-latency state transfer is crucial. We then examine studies for low-latency state transfer in edge clouds, considering limited computing and bandwidth resources.

Traditional approaches in centralized clouds involve cloning entire VMs [6] or containers [7] that run NFs. This approach includes transferring both NF states and redundant states, such as the ones of the operating system, which significantly increase migration times shown in [8]. Focusing on transferring only NF states, studies such as Pico [9] and S6 [10] provided libraries for NFs to manage their states, advocating direct state transfer between NF instances. Meanwhile, [11] used a key-value store to synchronize the state between NF instances. However, these approaches lack the ability to control state transfer *e.g.*, monitoring state transfer between NF instances to ensure correctness. To achieve greater control over state transfer, state management frameworks such as Split/Merge [2] and OpenNF [3] rely on a central controller exporting states from one NF and importing them into another NF. However, by fully involving the controller in the state transfer process, these studies potentially create a bottleneck, increasing bandwidth demands and state transfer time.

Towards low-latency state transfer in edge clouds, studies such as [4], [12], and [5] proposed frameworks that allow direct state transfers between NF instances without passing through the controller, thus reducing state transfer time. Subsequently, rather than directly engaging in state transfer, the controller coordinates various state operations, such as instructing a source NF to copy its states to a destination NF. While these frameworks have significantly enhanced state transfer time, the substantial modifications to NFs they require could potentially hinder their widespread adoption, highlighting the need to further exploit the potential benefits of state transfer.

III. BACKGROUND

A. NF State

While a stateful NF processes traffic, it generates historical processing values, such as variable values, which are referred to as NF states. NFs frequently read and write their states to ensure proper functioning. Taking an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) as an example, its states include lists of identified malicious nodes and packet statistics such as packet counts and timestamps of packet arrivals.

B. State Management Frameworks

Traditional use cases, such as scaling and fault tolerance, require that an NF instance transfers its states to another NF

instance. To ensure correct packet processing, it is essential for these use cases to transfer NF states consistently. However, NFs frequently change their states, thus highlighting the need to perform state management. Edge clouds often require migrating NFs following user's movement [13]. Subsequently, NF states must be consistent at the destination to ensure that NF runs at the exact progress it has before migration.

Notable state management frameworks such as FAST [5] utilize a three-layer architecture, from top to bottom, consisting of an application plane, a state control plane, and a data plane. This architectural approach is commonly employed in networking systems (*e.g.*, SDN) to separate control functions from data processing elements, thereby simplifying network management and fostering innovation [14]. The application plane hides technical details and allows control applications and external systems to perform management tasks. The state control plane acts as the central coordinator, managing NF states and facilitating communication between the application plane and the data plane. The state control plane includes: *i*) a state manager that handles state-related operations, *ii*) a state forwarding manager that controls the state transfer over the network, and *iii*) a flow forwarding manager that redirects the flow of user traffic to a destination NF after the state transfer is complete. The data plane processes and forwards user traffic, comprising both physical (*e.g.*, switches and servers) and virtual network elements (*e.g.*, virtual machines and Open vSwitches). NFs within the data plane provide essential processing capabilities and maintain the internal states needed for packet processing. Each NF uses a shared library to exchange states with other NFs.

To perform the state transfer, the state manager first sends a message to a source NF to transfer its states to a destination NF. The source NF then serializes its state objects as state messages and sends them to the destination NF via the state transfer path provided by the state forwarding manager. Upon receiving the state messages, the destination NF converts them into state objects and adds them to the local state store. Once this importing process is complete, the destination NF sends acknowledgment messages to the state manager. Afterwards, the flow manager updates the SDN switches, redirecting user traffic to the destination NF.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Our goal is to empower NFs with enhanced functionalities for various use cases such as accelerating packet processing and facilitating state transfer. To achieve this goal, we need a framework that allows the execution of custom processing with minimal NF modifications. This section details the system design and implementation of our proposed framework.

A. Idea

NFs are typically designed to handle specific tasks related to traffic processing. For example, a NAT translates IP addresses based on states (*i.e.*, entries) in its translation table. The concept of custom processing aims to extend the capabilities of NFs beyond their initial design scope by enabling the execution

of additional processing logic. We note that numerous studies about NF consolidation [15]–[17] aim to introduce custom processing to NFs. Unlike these studies that could potentially introduce incorrect behaviors to NFs, we ensure processing consistency by leveraging NF states to enable custom processing. Considering an SFC consisting of a firewall and a NAT, the custom processing in the firewall can obtain the states from the NAT to translate IP addresses at the beginning of the SFC. For collaborative robotics [18], by using custom processing, one robot can leverage the other robot’s states to coordinate movements, enabling efficient task collaboration. Furthermore, we demonstrate that custom processing can enhance state transfer in edge clouds. By enabling a destination NF to immediately process packets of a flow upon receiving its state, it eliminates the need to wait until the state transfer of all flows is complete. These examples show that empowering NFs with custom processing is practical and thus opens the door to supporting more use cases.

B. System Design

Fig. 1: The overall architecture of StateProc

Our goal is to leverage NF states to provide custom processing for NFs. We note that for custom processing an NF might cover functionalities of other NFs. Therefore, it is essential to coordinate processing between NFs to ensure consistency. Consequently, we need an entity that oversees and manages custom processes between NFs. We propose a processing manager within the controller to manage and coordinate the custom processing. Moreover, supporting custom processing requires modifying an NF, potentially leading to incorrect traffic processing within the NF. To reduce the required modification and ensure the correct execution of custom processing, we introduce a portable library for NFs.

We adopted a modular architecture to design our proposed framework. As shown in Fig.1, our proposed framework, StateProc, consists of three planes: an applications plane, a state control plane, and a data plane. At the control plane, we leveraged the components of FAST [5] including the state manager, state forwarding manager, and flow manager to handle the transfer of the states between NF instances and distribute user traffic accordingly. We introduce our novel processing manager component within the controller to coordinate

custom processing in NFs. It allows for executing commands for custom processing directly within NFs, extending their capabilities beyond their original functionalities. These custom processes can include packet processing actions such as dropping or buffering packets based on NF states. In the data plane, we develop a portable library integrated into NFs, allowing them to receive the custom processing commands from the processing manager and facilitate the execution of custom processes. Thanks to this library, NFs can be effectively and easily extended with minimal code modification, guaranteeing the correct behaviors of custom processing without disrupting their core operations.

Since custom processing requires acknowledging NF states, we aim to further improve StateProc to reduce the state transfer time. Achieving this goal is challenging due to the multiple tasks involved in transferring NF states. These tasks include exporting NF states from a source NF, transferring them over the network, importing them at the destination NF, and finally sending acknowledgments to the StateProc controller. Notably, the acknowledgment task significantly contributes to the state transfer time because the destination NF might be geographically far away from the StateProc controller. Moreover, the StateProc controller potentially becomes a bottleneck since it needs to parse and handle acknowledgment messages for the state transfer of multiple NFs. This issue is exacerbated considering the large number of states transferred between NFs located at various locations in edge clouds.

To overcome this challenge, we propose a novel state transfer workflow to lower state transfer time by reducing the number of transmissions and acknowledgments needed during the state transfer. First, we employ a batching technique that groups multiple states into one state message, thus reducing the number of transmissions. Moreover, we propose a preparation phase to pre-process the necessary states for transfer at the source NF during normal packet processing. This involves serializing and batching the states without disrupting the operations of the source NF, thus eliminating the need to perform these tasks during the state transfer. Finally, we allow the destination NF to directly acknowledge the receipts of states back to the source NF, rather than sending them to the stateProc controller. Once the source NF receives acknowledgments for all transferred states, it sends a final acknowledgment message to the StateProc controller, indicating the completion of the state transfer. This helps to digest acknowledgment messages sent to the StateProc controller, enhancing state transfer time.

For the state transfer workflow, the StateProc controller first initiates the preparation phase, where the source NF serializes its states and groups them into batches. During this phase, the processing manager dispatches custom processing commands to the source NF to *monitor* traffic and *track* modified states. Once the state transfer phase starts, the flow manager redirects user traffic to the destination NF. At the same time, the processing manager requests the destination NF to *buffer* incoming packets until the state transfer is complete. The destination NF then sends acknowledgments for all received

states to the source NF. After receiving all acknowledgments, the source NF sends a final acknowledgment to the StateProc controller to complete the state transfer.

C. Implementation

To implement StateProc, we expanded upon FAST [5], the well-known framework for state management in edge clouds. We opted for FAST due to its open-source design, programmability, and compatibility with various NFs.

1) *Custom Processing*: We extended FAST to support the execution of the custom processes. Initially, we introduced the novel processing manager in the FAST controller. Subsequently, we expanded the shared library to include the ability to execute custom commands issued by the processing manager. For the communication between the processing manager and the shared library, we used sockets for messages for custom processing. More specifically, we introduced a new channel called *ProcCommandChannel* (port 7794) for the processing manager to dispatch custom processing commands to NFs.

The processing manager in the StateProc controller requests an NF to execute various functions for custom processing. Specifically, the function *enable_new_flows_action(action)* is used to dispatch requests to an NF to monitor incoming traffic and take a specified action (e.g., drop or buffer) on packets belonging to new flows. The function *disable_new_flows_action* disables previously configured actions on new flows. Meanwhile, the function *start_buffer_processing(key, disableBuffer)* initiates the processing of packets matching a specific key within a buffer in the NF and optionally disables the buffer after completion. The function *drop_in_pkts* instructs an NF to drop all incoming packets matching a specific key. StateProc uses *track_prepared_flows* to track state changes between the preparation phase and the actual state transfer. StateProc is designed to facilitate adding new custom processing commands in the future. This makes StateProc versatile for various use cases, benefiting NFs by extending functionalities beyond their original design.

2) *State Transfer Workflow*: Our proposed state transfer workflow is divided into two phases: the preparation phase and the actual state transfer phase. For the preparation phase, the state manager in the StateProc controller indicates the source NF to execute the function *prepare_flows_for_transfer* to serialize states, group them in batches, and store them in a temporary buffer ready to be transferred directly later. During the preparation phase, the source NF continues processing traffic as usual, which may include modifying states that have already been prepared. To ensure the state consistency, the processing manager in StateProc requests the source NF to execute the function *track-prepared-flows* to monitor any changes to the prepared states by tracking incoming packets. Once the preparation phase is complete, an acknowledgment is sent to the controller to initiate the state transfer phase.

In the state transfer phase, the state manager tells the source NF to invoke the function *send_prepared_states_in_batches* to transfer the prepared states in batches to the destination NF.

Correspondingly, the destination NF executes the function *handle_put_perflow_batch*, to receive and process state batches. We used the standard TCP packet size as the batch size so each batch is sent as a single TCP packet. After receiving each state, the destination NF executes the function *start-buffer-processing* to process the buffered packets of the flow to which that state belongs. During the state transfer, the processing manager indicates the destination NF to execute the function *enable-new-flows-action(buffer)* or the function *drop-in-pkts* to buffer or drop incoming packets for each flow.

For the acknowledgment of the state transfer, the function *handle_put_perflow_batch* in the destination NF directly sends acknowledgments to the source NF. Simultaneously, the source NF executes the function *handle_put_perflow_batch_ack* to receive and count the acknowledgments. When the number of acknowledgments matches the number of state batches, the source NF sends a single acknowledgment to the StateProc controller, indicating the completion of the state transfer. Afterwards, if the function *enable-new-flows-action(buffer)* is executed earlier, the processing manager tells the destination NF to execute *disable-new-flows-action* to disable any configured actions for new flows, e.g., disabling the action that buffers packets of new flows arriving at the destination NF.

V. EVALUATION

This section investigates the performance of StateProc for state transfer under different guarantee modes in edge clouds. We specifically compare it against FAST, an efficient framework for state transfer in edge clouds. Moreover, we implemented an improved version of FAST that digests acknowledge messages for the state transfer, similar to StateProc. We detail the performance evaluation of StateProc compared to FAST and its improved version later in this section.

1) *Evaluated Guarantee Modes*: We examine the performance of the above studies considering a guarantee mode and no guarantees (NG) mode. In the guarantee mode, all packets arriving during the state transfer are properly processed, i.e., buffers are used to store packets until the state transfer is complete. In the NG mode, packets arriving during the state transfer are dropped, allowing for potential packet loss.

2) *Evaluation Metrics*: To assess the performance of StateProc against the other schemes, we employed the following three metrics:

- **State transfer time**: It is measured from the time that the controller initiates the state transfer command to the source NF to the time that the controller receives an acknowledgment for the completion of the state transfer.
- **Throughput**: It is measured by calculating how many packets the source NF processes in a second.
- **Packet processing latency**: It indicates any additional delay introduced by the shared library during normal packet processing within the source NF.

The above metrics demonstrate the efficiency of the studied schemes, reflecting service downtime, and are a commonly examined aspect in the existing literature [3], [5]. We analyze

the chosen metrics across various configurations, such as the number of active flows and different guarantee modes.

3) *Emulation Environment*: We leveraged a virtualized network testbed environment created using Mininet [19]. Mininet offers a convenient and efficient method to emulate network components by leveraging the Linux kernel and using real hardware resources to create hosts, switches, and links. Mininet is frequently used to mirror real-world network topologies. As demonstrated in [5], the results from both a real testbed and an emulated testbed using Mininet exhibit the same tendencies. Our experiments were conducted on a machine equipped with a 16-core AMD Ryzen 7 pro CPU (4.40GHz), 32GB of RAM, and running Ubuntu 22.04 LTS, mimicking the commodity server at the edge.

Our emulated testbed includes three switches and three hosts. Among the three switches, two switches are SDN-enabled switches used for the data network and the state transfer network, while the remaining switch is a normal switch used for the management network. Among the three hosts, two hosts acted as NF instances, and one host served as a traffic generator. The controller was run as a separate process before initiating the Mininet emulation. To evaluate the performance of the studied frameworks under realistic conditions, we chose the Passive Real-time Asset Detection System (PRADS) [20], a stateful NF, to provide traffic monitoring. Each state in PRADS contains packet header information and various counters, such as the total number of sent packets and the total number of sent bytes. The typical size of the states in PRADS is several hundred bytes.

4) *Measurement Process*: For each studied framework, we start the experiment by launching the controller, which listens for the readiness of data plane elements, such as SDN switches connecting to the flow manager and NFs connecting to the state manager. For the traffic generator, we used tcpreplay [21] to generate traffic by replaying a PCAP file captured from real network traffic. Then we ran PRADS on the source and destination NFs to monitor incoming traffic.

Since we assess the performance of the studied frameworks under the number of states, the controller initiates the state transfer after the source NF generates a specific number of states. In FAST, after the source NF identifies the states to be transferred, it serializes each state and transmits it to the destination NF. As each state is received, the destination NF sends an acknowledgment to the controller. Subsequently, the controller waits until all acknowledgments are received before updating the SDN switch to redirect user traffic to the destination NF. The improved FAST performs state transfer similarly to the original FAST but incorporates an optimized workflow for managing acknowledgments. For each received state, the destination NF sends the acknowledgment back to the source NF. Once the source NF has received all acknowledgments, it sends a single acknowledgment to the controller for the completion of the state transfer. StateProc transfers the states in two phases, including the preparation phase and the state transfer phase. In the preparation phase, the source

NF serializes the states and groups them in batches. Once the preparation phase is complete, the controller indicates the flow manager to update the SDN switch to redirect the user traffic of the moved flows to the destination NF. In the state transfer phase, the source NF sends state batches to the destination NF and listens for acknowledgments. When the source NF receives all acknowledgments for the state batches, it sends a final acknowledgment to the controller, indicating that the state transfer is complete.

A. Evaluation Results

Fig. 2: State transfer time (a) no guarantee mode, (b) guarantee mode

1) *State Transfer Time*: Our goal is to examine the performance of the studied frameworks in terms of state transfer time. Toward this goal, we investigate the transfer time for different numbers of states (65, 300, and 700) considering the guarantee mode and the NG mode. In the NG mode, the results plotted in Fig. 2(a) show that StateProc consistently achieved the lowest transfer time in all settings. For instance, with 300 states, StateProc achieves a transfer time of 9.63 ms, compared to 57.65 ms for FAST, representing an improvement of 83.3%. The improved FAST also improved the state transfer time by 33% when handling 300 states, compared to FAST. As expected, the superiority of the improved FAST over the original version demonstrates the efficiency of the optimized workflow for managing acknowledgments. Meanwhile, thanks to the proposed preparation phase, StateProc eliminates the need to serialize states at the source NF, thus reducing the time for the state transfer. Moreover, StateProc leverages custom processing to enhance the efficiency of the state transfer by monitoring state changes between the preparation phase and the actual state transfer, ensuring the consistency.

Fig. 2(b) shows the performance of the studied frameworks considering the guarantee mode. StateProc consistently demonstrated its superiority over the other frameworks in terms of the state transfer time. For instance, with 300 states, StateProc achieves a transfer time of 36 ms, compared to 423 ms for FAST, representing an improvement of 93%. The reason for this achievement is that StateProc uses an efficient buffering approach in the guaranteed mode. Unlike FAST which buffers packets at the controller until the state transfer is complete, StateProc uses the custom processing

to buffers packets right at the destination NF. Consequently, upon receiving the state of a flow, the destination NF can process packets from this flow without waiting for the states of all other flows to be received. We note the buffering approach in StateProc can facilitate large-scale deployment as the destination NF buffers packets during the state transfer.

Fig. 3: (a) Packet processing latency, (b) Throughput

2) *Packet Processing Latency and Throughput*: We aim to analyze how much overhead in terms of packet processing latency and throughput of NFs in StateProc. By comparing with FAST and its improved version, we examine the performance of StateProc under different numbers of states. The results in Fig. 3(a) show that the packet processing latency of StateProc remains similar to the FAST and the improved FAST in all settings. For instance, with 300 states, the packet processing latency for StateProc is 1.525 us compared to 1.498 us for FAST, representing a small difference of less than 0.03 ms. Similarly, the throughput results in Fig. 3(b) indicate that StateProc achieves comparable throughput to FAST for the NF. For example, the throughput of StateProc is 1151 pkt/sec compared to 1157 pkt/sec for FAST when sending 300 states, resulting in only 0.005% difference. As expected, our library for the NF introduces insignificant overhead on the packet processing.

In summary, the observations from the above results collectively support our expectation that StateProc achieves significant performance gains in terms of the transfer time by leveraging NF states for custom processing, without experiencing additional processing overhead.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces StateProc, a novel state management framework that employs NF states to enhance the processing capabilities of NFs. StateProc provides APIs through the processing manager to allow for executing custom logic beyond the original functionalities of NFs. We demonstrate the support of custom processing in StateProc for the transfer of NF states. The results show that StateProc significantly reduces the state transfer time compared to FAST, a notable state management framework in edge clouds. Moreover, StateProc introduces minimal processing overhead to NFs, thus facilitating a wide range of innovative use cases.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (HORIZON-MSCA-2022-DN-01) project TOAST under the grant agreement No. 101073465, and supported in part by the German Research Foundation (DFG, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) as part of Germany’s Excellence Strategy — EXC 2050/1 – Project ID 390696704 – Cluster of Excellence “Centre for Tactile Internet with Human-in-the-Loop” (CeTI) of Technische Universität Dresden and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research of Germany in the programme of “Souverän. Digital. Vernetzt.” Joint project 6G-life, project identification number: 16KISK001K.

REFERENCES

- [1] “Cloud firewall, <https://aws.amazon.com/network-firewall/>,” accessed on May 30, 2024.
- [2] S. Rajagopalan *et al.*, “{Split/Merge}: System support for elastic execution in virtual middleboxes,” in *USENIX NSDI*, 2013, pp. 227–240.
- [3] A. Gember-Jacobson *et al.*, “Opennf: Enabling innovation in network function control,” *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Communication Review*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 163–174, 2014.
- [4] J. Sherry *et al.*, “Rollback-recovery for middleboxes,” *ACM SIGCOMM Computer Commun. Rev.*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 227–240, Aug. 2015.
- [5] T. V. Doan *et al.*, “Fast: Flexible and low-latency state transfer in mobile edge computing,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 115 315–115 334, 2021.
- [6] C. Clark *et al.*, “Live migration of virtual machines,” in *USENIX NSDI*, 2005.
- [7] C. Puliafito *et al.*, “Container migration in the fog: A performance evaluation,” *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 7, p. 1488, 2019.
- [8] T. V. Doan *et al.*, “Containers vs virtual machines: Choosing the right virtualization technology for mobile edge cloud,” in *2019 IEEE 2nd 5G World Forum (5GWF)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 46–52.
- [9] S. Rajagopalan *et al.*, “Pico replication: A high availability framework for middleboxes,” in *Proceedings of the 4th annual Symposium on Cloud Computing*, 2013, pp. 1–15.
- [10] S. Woo *et al.*, “Elastic scaling of stateful network functions,” in *Proc. USENIX NSDI*, 2018, pp. 299–312.
- [11] T. V. Doan *et al.*, “Seamless service migration framework for autonomous driving in mobile edge cloud,” in *2020 IEEE 17th Annual Consumer Communications Networking Conference (CCNC)*, 2020, pp. 1–2.
- [12] T. V. Doan *et al.*, “Stateos: Enabling versatile network function virtualization in edge clouds,” in *NOMS 2024-2024 IEEE Network Operations and Management Symposium*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–9.
- [13] T. V. Doan *et al.*, “Follow me, if you can: A framework for seamless migration in mobile edge cloud,” in *IEEE INFOCOM 2020-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WK-SHPS)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1178–1183.
- [14] J. Xie *et al.*, “Control plane of software defined networks: A survey,” *Computer communications*, vol. 67, pp. 1–10, 2015.
- [15] Y. Jiang *et al.*, “Speedybox: Low-latency nfv service chains with cross-nf runtime consolidation,” in *2019 IEEE 39th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)*.
- [16] Z. Meng *et al.*, “Micronf: An efficient framework for enabling modularized service chains in nfv,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*.
- [17] S. R. Chowdhury *et al.*, “A disaggregated packet processing architecture for network function virtualization,” *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*.
- [18] Z. Fan *et al.*, “Collaborative robot transport system based on edge computing,” in *CYBER*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1320–1326.
- [19] “Mininet, An Instant Virtual Network on your Laptop (or other PC), <http://mininet.org/>,” accessed on April. 7, 2024.
- [20] “PRADS, Passive Real-time Asset Detection System, <http://gamelinux.github.io/prads/>,” accessed on Feb. 07, 2020.
- [21] “Tcpreplay, An Open Source Network Security Monitoring Tool, <https://tcpreplay.appneta.com/>,” accessed on Jan. 20, 2121.